

**SCIENTIFIC LEADER: ABOUT SAID AHMAD'S WORK "KORAKOZ
MAJNUN"**

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Abstract: In the end, we can say that this story of Said Ahmed is a touching story that will bring tears to the eyes of any reader.

Key words: Hope, pity, loyalty, faith, hatred.

"Whoever of you turns away from his religion and dies in this disbelief, then their (meritful) deeds will be null and void, and they will be the people of Hell and will remain there forever."

"One of the ten animals that will enter Paradise is the faithful dog of Ash'abi Kahf."

The gaze of an artistic writer is different from the gaze of ordinary people. He clearly and clearly sees the very subtle aspects of human nature, not only human, but also animal characteristics.

"Karakoz Majnun" is one of the best stories written by Said Ahmed during the years of independence. He waits for Borikhan. He remembers him in the morning prayer on the day God gave him.

Saodat Aya's nature is full of thoughtfulness, like thinking about the world of true Uzbek Muslim grandmothers. The old woman who heard the news of her son from her grandson Anvar becomes sad. Adib describes this change in the old woman: "He broke down and stayed at home without crossing the threshold," he explains.

One day, Saodat goes to her daughter's house with her dog Karakoz. We pay attention to the process of their arrival and departure. Let's say that they are "manly by sticking one ear and slapping the other", "chasing cats" on the road, "joking at the music in the trees" - all of them are skillfully described. That's why he looked at his dog and said: "Shall we go to your brother Abdumalik's house, or to your sister Dollar's? Your dear sister Dilbar lives in the house. She is careful of the dog. She won't let you into her house. What are we going to do now? Okay, let's go to her. We won't sleep. The children are in the yard until I leave. "You are playing with him," he says casually. Along the way, Saodat chats with the old woman's dog and returns to his tracks.

When he returns home, a strange news is waiting for him. Bori Khan has come, that is, the old woman has "disappeared now". He had to fulfill his dreams, which were pressing like a mountain. However, reality takes a different color. The meeting of mother and child...

It is interesting that in this process the dog is disturbed for some reason, he feels something; that's why "the notary keeps snarling at the person". In his mother's arms, Borikhon is like a stranger. Because "he smelled of vodka and a house with candles". The happy mother does not pay attention to this at first. It is known that Bori Khan's ancestors returned from Islam and adopted another religion.

For the mother, religion, national-religious values, and patriotism are above all else. That's why she is disappointed with Bori Khan, and she leaves him to be gone; Ketar Mahali turns away from him. Now the mother does not remember her son in the morning prayer.

The story tells about Saodat Aya's beautiful youth, the birth of Bori Khan, and the wonderful history of his unpleasant deeds that upset his mother while traveling in other countries.

Even at the place of her death, Saodat Aya's understanding of the meaning of life, the event of coming and going to this world in a very natural-Muslim manner is clearly visible in the will she made to her children and grandchildren.

Of course, during the reading of the story, we found out what the Black-eyed madman in the title is. Yes, this is the one that the writer lovingly described as "a small one with two belt-like stripes, one black and one brown." "a dog with a black muzzle and two black eyes, and a blunt eyebrow above one eye." Saodat is almost in the same mood as the old woman: when she is sad, she is sad, when she is happy, she is happy. Rihon is more alien to Saodat than a dog.

In the story, after the death of the old woman Saodat, the writer draws two drops of tears on her black eyes with a sharp pencil in order to convey the spirit of Karakoz to the readers. The death of the madman Karakoz at the end of the story makes the reader sad.

At the beginning of the story, a verse from the Qur'anic Surah "Baqara" is quoted as an epigraph. It is easy to understand that these excerpts refer to the character of Bori Khan in the story. Karakoz, who is depicted as a conscious and intelligent person, refers to Majnun, of course.

The story contains a lot of meaning. The value of Uzbek traditions is emphasized by showing the actions of an unworthy child. In fact, the dog's loyalty destroys the mother's heart of a son. standing in relatively high spiritual ranks will always gain glory.

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